

Área: ANA

Monitoramento participativo de ambientes aquáticos urbanos em Foz do Iguaçu, Paraná.

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Highlights

Participatory Monitoring of Urban Aquatic Environments in Foz do Iguaçu/PR – Participatory monitoring in Foz do Iguaçu evaluated water quality and biodiversity, revealing altered physicochemical parameters, low biological diversity, and significant urban impacts.

Resumo/Abstract

Urbanization and population growth impose major challenges on environmental management, including the occupation of green areas, channeling of streams, and degradation of riparian vegetation. Such transformations alter aquatic habitats and directly affect water quality through increased nutrient loads and untreated domestic sewage. In this context, participatory monitoring emerges as an important strategy for community engagement in environmental conservation, fostering dialogue between science, management, and society. This study aimed to apply and disseminate participatory monitoring methodologies to evaluate the ecological condition of green areas and urban aquatic environments in Foz do Iguaçu, Paraná, Brazil. The project was carried out in two stages: (1) the *1st Workshop on Participatory Monitoring of Urban Aquatic Environments* (March 26–28, 2025), involving students, public managers, government institutions, and representatives from six Latin American countries; and (2) the application of six participatory monitoring methodologies in the *Parque Natural Municipal Córrego Brasília*, in partnership with the local quilombola community. Water samples were analyzed for physicochemical parameters such as pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity, dissolved oxygen, nitrate, and phosphate, and the results were compared with the limits established by CONAMA Resolution 357/2005. Biological analyses were based on the diversity of benthic macroinvertebrates, used as bioindicators of water quality. The results indicated that, in the Córrego Brasília, several parameters approached or exceeded the legal limits, reflecting the influence of nearby pig farming, channelization, and urban runoff. The predominance of pollution-tolerant macroinvertebrates and the low presence of sensitive taxa revealed reduced biological diversity. Additionally, field observations recorded solid waste accumulation, erosion, sedimentation, and riparian vegetation degradation. In contrast, data collected during the workshop showed that the Iguaçu River presented more stable physicochemical parameters and higher biological diversity than the Mathias Almada River, which exhibited greater anthropogenic impacts. These findings confirm that participatory monitoring is an effective tool for evaluating urban environmental quality, raising community awareness, and promoting collaborative action in the conservation of aquatic ecosystems.

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